

CIRCADIAN RHYTHM DISORDERS

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Abstract. *Circadian rhythm disorders are disruptions in the body's internal clock, affecting sleep-wake cycles and various physiological processes. This article provides a detailed examination of circadian rhythms, their biological underpinnings, and the impact of their disruption on health and wellbeing. The article categorizes types of circadian rhythm disorders, such as Delayed Sleep Phase Disorder (DSPD), Advanced Sleep Phase Disorder (ASPD), Shift Work Disorder, and Jet Lag.*

It also explores the causes, symptoms, and potential consequences of these disorders, including increased risk for mental health issues, cardiovascular diseases, and metabolic disorders. Treatment options, including behavioral interventions, light therapy, and pharmacological approaches, are discussed. Understanding circadian rhythm disorders is crucial for developing effective management strategies and promoting overall health.

Keywords: *Circadian rhythm, sleep disorders, internal clock, health impact, treatment.*

РАССТРОЙСТВА ЦИРКАДНОГО РИТМА

Аннотация. *Расстройства циркадного ритма — это нарушения внутренних часов организма, влияющие на циклы сна и бодрствования и различные физиологические процессы. В этой статье подробно рассматриваются циркадные ритмы, их биологические основы и влияние их нарушения на здоровье и благополучие. В статье классифицируются типы расстройств циркадного ритма, такие как расстройство задержки фазы сна (DSPD), расстройство опережающей фазы сна (ASPD), расстройство сменной работы и смена часовых поясов.*

В ней также изучаются причины, симптомы и потенциальные последствия этих расстройств, включая повышенный риск проблем с психическим здоровьем, сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний и нарушений обмена веществ. Обсуждаются варианты лечения, включая поведенческие вмешательства, светотерапию и фармакологические подходы.

Понимание расстройств циркадного ритма имеет решающее значение для разработки эффективных стратегий управления и укрепления общего здоровья.

Ключевые слова: *циркадный ритм, расстройства сна, внутренние часы, влияние на здоровье, лечение.*

Introduction:

Circadian rhythms regulate numerous bodily functions, including sleep, hormone release, and metabolism. Disruptions to these rhythms can lead to significant health issues.

Biological Basis of Circadian Rhythms

Circadian rhythms are controlled by the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN) in the brain, which responds to light and regulates hormonal and behavioral patterns.

Types of Circadian Rhythm Disorders

- Delayed Sleep Phase Disorder (DSPD): Difficulty falling asleep early and waking up.
- Advanced Sleep Phase Disorder (ASPD): Early sleep onset and wakefulness.
- Shift Work Disorder: Disruption due to work schedules that conflict with natural sleep patterns.
- Jet Lag: Temporary condition resulting from rapid travel across time zones.

Causes and Symptoms

Causes include genetics, lifestyle factors, and exposure to artificial light. Symptoms range from insomnia and excessive daytime sleepiness to mood disturbances.

Health Impacts

Circadian rhythm disorders are linked to various negative health outcomes, including depression, anxiety, obesity, and cardiovascular diseases.

Treatment and Management

Treatments may involve cognitive-behavioral therapy for insomnia (CBT-I), light therapy, melatonin supplementation, and lifestyle modifications focusing on regular sleep patterns.

Conclusion:

Awareness of circadian rhythm disorders is crucial for identifying at-risk populations and implementing effective interventions, thereby improving public health outcomes.

REFERENCES

1. Young, T. & Peppé, S. (2017). Circadian Rhythm Disorders: Diagnosis and Treatment. *Sleep Medicine Reviews*, 31, 22-29.
2. American Academy of Sleep Medicine. (2014). *The International Classification of Sleep Disorders*.
3. Reid, K. J. et al. (2015). Circadian Rhythms and Sleep Disorders: A Complex Relationship. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*, 11(2), 225-229.
4. Schmidt, C., & Collette, F. (2019). Circadian Disruption and Health: A Critical Review of the Evidence. *Sleep Medicine Reviews*, 48, 101211.
5. Lockley, S. W., & Foster, R. G. (2012). Sleep and Circadian Rhythm Disruption in Psychiatric Disorders. *Sleep Medicine Clinics*, 7(3), 479-490.